

CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CITIZENSHIP AND GENERAL COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the issues such as the analysis of pedagogical and psychological aspects of the processes of using electronic environment in the development of civil and general-purpose competences in students on the basis of innovative approaches, the use of electronic environment in the development of civil and general-purpose competences in students, improvement of the quality and effectiveness of professional training. Also, the process of using the electronic environment for the development of civil compensations in students by optimizing the requirements of universal competency to the requirements of social order has been discussed.*

Keywords: *legal consciousness, legal culture, civil position, competence, values, public culture*

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the formation of a society consisting of young people who not only know their rights and freedoms and obligations well, who can exercise these rights and freedoms and conscientiously approach their obligations, who can respect the rights and freedoms of others, who have a high legal culture and an active citizenship position is a state policy level. is among the issues.

The Strategy of Actions on five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4947 dated February 7, 2017, initiated qualitatively new approaches to the strategic planning system of the country's state and society development perspective. In point 4 of the second priority direction of the action strategy, raising the legal culture and consciousness of the population is considered as the main priority direction. In addition, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech entitled "Constitution is a free and prosperous life, a strong foundation for the further development of our country" at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 26th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan focused on preparing young people to live in civil society, developing an active social citizenship position in them, general culture the task of formation was determined.

In the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the fundamental improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society", it was criticized that, first of all, work on legal education and training is not carried out systematically and organically in raising legal culture. That is, "the formation of civil competences in relation to the factors that have a negative impact on the legal education of young people, respect for laws and rules of etiquette, loyalty to national values, and a sense of intolerance towards offenses were not comprehensively approached." In the presidential decree, the concept of "Raising legal culture in society" was developed based on the conceptual idea "High legal culture is a guarantee of the country's development". In it: "The main goal of the Concept is to achieve legal literacy of all layers of the population, to create a comprehensive regular system of educating citizens who are

strong-willed, who know their rights and respect the law, who can apply their legal knowledge in everyday life, who have an active citizenship position and who are intolerant of crime." - it is said. This calls for an active citizenship position in higher education institutions and the creation of new, modern forms, the development of modernizing and improvement measures, the creation of new, modern forms, scientific research of the possibilities of using new pedagogical technologies in the formation of legal culture, and the formation of legal culture.

Socially active civic competence means being aware of events and happenings in the state and society, actively participating in these processes, clearly knowing one's civil rights and duties, observing them, being able to demonstrate general cultural skills, and having legal culture.

The development of civic and general cultural competences among students is one of the urgent issues of today, because today a number of destructive groups are operating in the territories of the countries of the world, causing a number of problems in the political, socio-cultural, and educational life of these countries. According to information, the number of terrorist acts is increasing every year, in 2018 alone, 15,300 terrorist attacks were committed in the world; Every 40 seconds, one person on earth commits suicide, almost a million people die every year due to suicide.

Large-scale reforms in the social, spiritual, political and economic spheres in our country in recent years, and global changes in the world have put a number of tasks to be solved before the state and society. The increasing flow of destructive information, the changing moral and ethical values of the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan require the development of civic and general cultural competences at the individual, group and community level. According to the decision of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 12, 2019, the fact that 40 Uzbek-language profiles, channels and pages on the global information network were declared extremist and terrorist also indicates the need to solve this problem. Head of State Sh. Mirziyoev "Of course, we are doing great work on educating young people who think independently, have modern knowledge and skills, and have a strong life position. But to be honest, if we take into account the intense struggle to capture the minds and hearts of the population, especially young people, and the growing threats such as religious extremism, terrorism, drug addiction, and "mass culture" all over the world today, our children's education, spiritual- "It is necessary not to slow down our work in the field of education, on the contrary, to raise it to a new level [5]" and defined the tasks that should be implemented in the development of civic and general cultural competences in students.

Analyzing the activity of destructive religious, extremist and terrorist currents and groups, which have a negative impact on the stability of the Republic of Uzbekistan, more specifically, its social and spiritual development, developing civic and general cultural competences, defining the genesis, essence and content of concepts based on existing scientific theories, classification, creation and improvement of a certain socio-psychological basis for the development of civic and general cultural competences in students are among the important tasks facing the science of pedagogy. This issue, that is, the problem of studying the socio-pedagogical features of the development of civic and general cultural competences in students, was not a separate object of research. Currently, the socio-pedagogical study of the causes of the emergence of destructive ideas and groups, the expansion of the scope of activities, is of urgent theoretical and practical importance.

As a result of improving the technology of using the electronic environment in the development of civic and general cultural competences in students, it is necessary to emphasize the following:

Modern scientific and technical development, integration of science and production requires extensive use of information and communication technology capabilities. Such an urgent social phenomenon creates the need to improve the technology of using the electronic environment in the development of civic and general cultural competences among students, because civic engagement of future specialists in their professional activities, awareness of national and universal values is the guarantee of their development as high-potential personnel.

The future professional competence of the future specialists is clearly visible in their manifestation as active citizens, in their efforts for the development of the country and the development of science and technology. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the implementation of research on increasing the efficiency of the scientific system of its development.

To have an active citizenship position means to treat with infinite respect the traditions, moral standards, lifestyle, high spirituality, material and spiritual wealth, historical heritage, traditions, all historical achievements and lessons of our people created over the centuries. With the development of information and communication technologies and the electronic educational environment, using tools such as video conferencing, social networks and discussion forums, expanding the possibilities of organizing the educational process in active interaction with educational subjects, being able to implement it during their practical activities, as well as the duty to their country and, realizing their obligations, it is necessary to develop general cultural competences in their full implementation.

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